

QUALITY OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE AMONG TEACHERS AND THEIR PERFORMANCE IN FACE-TO-FACE CLASSES

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Quality of Work-Life Balance among Teachers and their Performance in Face-To-Face Classes

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Abstract

This study, conducted in South and North Madalum District Schools, Division of Lanao del Sur II, during the school year 2022-2023, employed a descriptive correlational research design to explore the quality of work-life balance among teachers and its impact on their performance in face-to-face classes. The research focused on selected schools in Madalum, Lanao del Sur, Philippines, with 100 elementary and primary school teachers participating. The study revealed that the majority of teachers were in the 36-40 years age group, female, married, held a Master's Degree, and had less than 5 years of teaching experience. The study also revealed a satisfactory perception of work-life balance, personal-life balance, and family-life balance among teachers. Regarding teaching performance, more than half of the respondents received an outstanding rating, indicating a high level of satisfaction and competence. Moreover, there was a significant and negative relationship between the perceived quality of work-life balance and teaching performance rejecting the null hypothesis of the study. In contrast, the variables related to personal-life balance and family-life balance did not show a significant relationship with teaching performance. However, a critical finding emerged, revealing a significant and negative relationship between the perceived quality of work-life balance and teaching performance. Teachers reporting lower work-life balance were more likely to exhibit poorer teaching performance. It was recommended that counselling services and mentoring programs may be provided for teachers to assist them in managing their professional and personal responsibilities.

Keywords: *face-to-face classes, teaching performance, personal-life balance, work-life balance*

Introduction

As the educational landscape evolves, new challenges arise, and the recent COVID-19 pandemic has further complicated the delicate balance teachers strive to maintain. Work-life balance is a term that encapsulates the equilibrium between an individual's professional responsibilities and personal life pursuits. In today's fast-paced and demanding world, achieving and maintaining this balance has become a critical concern for individuals across various professions and industries. The teaching profession is one of the cornerstones of society, playing a pivotal role in shaping the future of nations. The quality of education delivered to students is inextricably linked to the well-being and job satisfaction of teachers. Achieving an optimal work-life balance is essential for educators to perform at their best in the classroom (Wong, 2019).

The quality of work-life balance is a crucial issue that affects the overall well-being of teachers. It refers to the balance between work-related responsibilities and personal life, including family, leisure, and social activities. Maintaining a good work-life balance is critical for teachers' mental and physical health, job satisfaction, and overall job performance. However, in recent years, there has been growing basis about the impact of poor work-life balance on teachers' performance, particularly in face-to-face classes. With the COVID-19 pandemic forcing teachers to adapt to new teaching methods, the issue has become even more relevant (Shao & Skelton, 2018).

Research showed that teachers' work-life balance has a significant impact on their job performance, motivation, and retention. A study by Piryani and Gow (2019) found that teachers who had a better work-life balance reported higher job satisfaction and lower levels of burnout. On the other hand, teachers who had a poor work-life balance were more likely to experience burnout, stress, and job dissatisfaction, which can negatively impact their students' learning outcomes.

DepEd Memorandum Order (DMO) No. 291, s. 2008 was implemented among schools to ensure that public teachers render only the required number of teaching loads needed from them. The memorandum provides that teachers shall render at most six hours (6) of actual classroom teaching a day, except when undertaking academic activities that require presence outside the school premises. This ensures that teachers are given two hours to use for their other matters. This memorandum also prevents teachers from overtime work and attain work-life balance.

In connection, it was a significant policy implemented in the Philippines to safeguard the well-being and work-life balance of public-school teachers. Its key provisions aimed to regulate the workload of teachers to ensure they could effectively carry out their responsibilities without excessive overtime work. The memorandum stipulated that public-school teachers should not be required to conduct more than six hours of actual classroom teaching per day. This limitation was crucial in preventing teacher burnout and fatigue, allowing educators to deliver quality instruction without being overburdened. While the maximum teaching hours were set at six, the memorandum recognized that there might be academic activities that require teachers' presence outside of regular classroom teaching. This provision acknowledged that teachers often engage in extracurricular activities, meetings, or events that contribute to the overall educational experience for students.

By ensuring teachers have a maximum of six teaching hours, DMO No. 291 effectively provided teachers with two hours of personal time during the school day. This time could be used for various purposes, such as lesson planning, grading, professional development,

and addressing administrative tasks. This allocation contributed to a better work-life balance for educators. The memorandum aimed to curb excessive overtime work for teachers, which is a common issue in the field of education. By setting clear limits on teaching hours, it helped prevent teachers from being overworked and allowed them to maintain a healthier work-life balance.

Despite the growing body of research on work-life balance among teachers, there are still several gaps in our understanding of the issue. For example, there is a need for more research that explores the impact of work-life balance on teacher performance in face-to-face classes specifically. Furthermore, there is a lack of research that examines the factors that contribute to poor work-life balance among teachers. Hence, the objective of this study was to investigate the relationship between work-life balance and teacher performance in face-to-face classes. The study was conducted in South Madalum District and North Madalum District, Division of Lanao del Sur II during the School Year 2022-2023. The study findings were disseminated through academic publications and presentations at conferences. The study aimed to provide insights that can help schools improve teacher well-being and overall job performance.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to investigate the quality of work-life balance among teachers and their performance in South and North Madalum District, Division of Lanao del Sur II, School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following problems:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. plantilla position; and
 - 1.6. number of years in service?
2. What is the teachers' level on the quality of their work-life balance in terms of:
 - 2.1. work-life balance;
 - 2.2. personal work-life balance; and
 - 2.3. family life balance?
3. What is the teaching performance of the respondents based on Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) rating for school year 2022-2023?
4. Is there a significant difference between the quality of work-life balance among teachers when they are grouped according to profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the quality of work-life balance among teachers and their teaching performance?
6. What action plan can be implemented based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The research employed a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the work-life balance quality of teachers and its impact on their performance during face-to-face classes in South and North Madalum District Schools, Division of Lanao del Sur II, for the school year 2022-2023. This approach involves a combination of descriptive and correlational methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the variables under investigation (Gabriel, 2020). Descriptive research was chosen because it is well-suited for providing a detailed portrayal of the current state or condition of a particular phenomenon or problem. In this case, it allowed the study to gain insight into the work-life balance quality among teachers in the specified school districts. Correlational research, on the other hand, was employed to determine and analyze any existing relationships between multiple variables. Specifically, the study sought to establish a correlation between the quality of work-life balance experienced by teachers and their performance in face-to-face classroom settings.

Respondents

The respondents in this research were carefully chosen to ensure a representative and diverse sample. The South Madalum District has an official total enrolment for the school year 2022-2023 of 1499 learners with 86 teaching personnel. However, in North Madalum District has a total enrolment of 919 learners with 49 teaching personnel.

One hundred elementary and primary school teachers were randomly selected from both South and North Madalum District Schools, which fall under the purview of the Division of Lanao del Sur II, during the school year 2022-2023. In conducting the study, there are 24 male respondents and 76 female respondents. The sampling procedure employed in this study aimed to provide a comprehensive perspective on the quality of work-life balance among teachers and its impact on their performance in face-to-face classrooms.

To prevent bias and ensure fairness, a random sampling method was used. This involved assigning a unique identifier (e.g., a number) to each eligible teacher in the population. A random selection process, such as drawing lots, was then employed to select the 100

participants from this pool. This step ensured that each teacher had an equal chance of being selected, enhancing the study's representativeness.

Additionally, the selected schools in the South and North District were listed below. In South District, all elementary and primary schools were included containing of six schools comprising 69 total teachers, while in North District all elementary and primary schools were also included containing of eight schools comprising 40 total teachers. The table below presents the actual number of teachers per school, number of respondents per school, and the percentage:

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

<i>List of Schools</i>	<i>Actual No. of Teachers</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
SOUTH DISTRICT			
Madalum Central Elementary School	28	25	89.28%
Madaya Elementary School	8	8	100%
Kormatan Elementary School	15	13	86.66%
Sugod Elementary School	10	10	100%
Bubong Primary School	4	4	100%
Linuk Primary School	4	4	100%
NORTH DISTRICT			
Pagayawan Central Elementary School	13	11	84.61%
Salongabanding Elementary School	7	5	71.42%
Liangan Primary School	4	4	100%
Sabanding Primary School	4	4	100%
Cadayonan Primary School	3	3	100%
Tongantongan Primary School	3	3	100%
Raya Primary School	4	4	100%
Cabasaran Primary School	2	2	100%
Total	109	100	

Random sampling is a method of selecting respondents for a research study in which each member of the population has an equal chance of being included in the sample. In this case, the researcher planned to randomly select 100 primary and elementary teachers from South and North Madalum District, Division of Lanao del Sur II, during the School Year 2022-2023. Random sampling was considered a reliable and valid method for selecting respondents in research studies as it helped to ensure that the sample was representative of the population, which enhanced the generalizability of the findings to the larger population. By randomly selecting participants, the researcher could minimize bias and increase the external validity of the study.

Instruments

To measure the work-life balance of teachers, this study used an adapted questionnaire based on the study by Akgunduz et al., (2019). The questionnaire serves as the basis for collecting data on various aspects of the teachers' work-life balance. Additionally, the performance of teachers was evaluated using the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) ratings during the school year 2022-2023.

The questionnaire consists of two parts, part 1 was gathering demographic profile of the respondents. Part 2, teachers on the quality of their work-life balance. Part 1 of the questionnaire included the profile of the teachers including their age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching position/designation, and number of years in service. Part 2 focused on collecting information related to teachers' work-life balance. It included several sections with statements related to different aspects of work-life balance. The first section on part 2 consisting of seven items, while the second and third sections consists of ten items each, also and teachers are asked to rate their agreement or disagreement with these statements using a 4-point scale ranging from, 4-Strongly agree, 3-Agree, 2-Disagree, and 1-Strongly Disagree.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaires, it was presented to the panel members for corrections and evaluated the appropriateness of the research instrument and provided feedback and comments to refine the final research instrument. Their comments and suggestions were to separate family from work, to discuss the research instrument scoring procedure how to give points for negative item statements, and the presence of negative and positive statements (Role overload items are stated negatively, while the rest are positively stated). After the consultation about the questionnaire, pilot testing was conducted at Madamba Central Elementary school, Lower Madamba District, Division of Lanao del Sur II, to 20 teachers to test the internal consistency of the questionnaire.

Table 2. *Reliability Statistics Result*

<i>Study Variable</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>No. of Items</i>	<i>Description</i>
Quality of Work-Life Balance	0.940	27	Excellent
Work-Life Balance	0.794	7	Acceptable
Personal-Life Balance	0.906	10	Excellent
Family-Life Balance	0.890	10	Good

Legend: ≥ 0.90 , Excellent; $0.80-0.89$, Good; $0.70-0.79$, Acceptable; $0.60-0.69$, Questionable; $0.50-0.59$, Poor; ≤ 0.49 , Unacceptable
Note: Cronbach's Alpha above 0.7 is considered reliable

The reliability statistics result shows Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for the study variables. Cronbach's Alpha is a measure of internal consistency, which indicates how well the items in a scale or questionnaire are measuring the same construct. In general, Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.7 are considered reliable, and values above 0.9 are excellent. Based on this criterion, the study variable in the study is considered reliable, with Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.7. For the work-life balance variable, items 1, 3, and 8 must be deleted so that Cronbach's alpha value is 0.794 and considered "acceptable".

Thus, the instrument used in this study has at least good internal consistency, indicating that it can be used for future research purposes.

Procedure

The data gathering procedure for this study involved several steps to ensure that the data collected was reliable and accurate. First, permission was sought from the Schools Division Superintendent of Lanao del Sur II, the Public Schools Division Supervisor of South and North Madalum District, and the school heads of the selected primary and elementary schools to properly ask for permission to conduct the study. This was to ensure that the study was aligned with the policies and regulations of the school and division.

After obtaining permission, the primary and elementary teachers in South and North Madalum District, Division of Lanao del Sur II were provided with informed consent forms that explained the purpose of the study, expected duration of the interview, confidentiality of information shared, and voluntary nature of their participation. The study adhered to ethical considerations, including obtaining consent, maintaining confidentiality, and ensuring voluntary participation. It was important to obtain informed consent from the participants to ensure that they are aware of the study's purpose and their rights as participants.

The distribution of the survey questionnaire was scheduled and stated in the informed consents signed by the respondents. Individual distribution of the questionnaire was not performed due to time limitations. After the completion of the survey, the questionnaires were retrieved, and the data collected were analyzed using statistical software. The teaching performance of the teachers were obtained through the teacher's rating in the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) during the SY 2022-2023 which were provided through the respective school records with the consent of the school principals. Confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were maintained throughout the study, and results were presented in aggregate form with no individual respondent information revealed.

Data Analysis

These statistical tools can help provide insights and interpretations of the data gathered from the study, and can help answer the research questions and objectives.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This was used to describe the profile of the respondents and their teaching performance based on IPCRF.

Mean and Standard Deviation. This was used to calculate and describe the work-life balance of the teachers.

Analysis of variance (ANOVA). This can be used to determine if there is significant difference between work-life balance of teachers when grouped according to profile.

Regression. This can be used to determine if there is a relationship between dependent variable and one or more independent variables.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyses, results, and discussions of the data gathered by the researcher.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, designation, and number of years in service?

Table 3. Age

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-22	2	2.0
23-30	21	21.0
31-35	22	22.0
36-40	24	24.0
41-49	16	16.0
50-65	15	15.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3 presents the distribution of respondents' ages. The largest age group in the sample is the 36-40 years category, comprising 24 respondents, or 24.0% of the total while the least percentage of respondents comprising 2% were between 18-22 years old.

This suggests a significant representation of individuals in their late thirties and early forties. Thus, the age distribution in this survey sample is quite diverse, covering a wide range of age groups. The majority of respondents are in their thirties and forties, while younger and older age groups are less represented.

The diverse age distribution observed in the survey aligns with findings from previous research on the demographic profiles of teachers. For instance, (Ying et al. 2020) conducted a comprehensive study on teacher demographics, emphasizing the importance of understanding age-related trends in the profession. In their research, they found that teachers in their thirties and forties often constitute a significant portion of the workforce, a trend mirrored in the current study's prominent 36-40 years age group (24.0%).

Table 4. Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	24	24.0
Female	76	76.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4 presents the distribution of respondents' sex in the survey. The data shows that the majority of respondents in the sample identify as Female, with 76 respondents, accounting for 76.0% of the total. In contrast, the Male category comprises 24 respondents, making up 24.0% of the sample. This sex distribution reveals a significant sex imbalance in the sample, with a much higher representation of female respondents compared to males.

A study by Syrek (2022) highlighted that sex dynamics within the teaching profession can influence various aspects of educators' lives, including job satisfaction and stress levels. The significant overrepresentation of female respondents in this study may warrant further investigation into how sex-related factors contribute to the perceived quality of work-life balance among teachers.

Table 5. Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	21	21.0
Married	74	74.0
Separated	2	2.0
Widowed	3	3.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5 presents the distribution of respondents' civil status in the survey.

As presented in the results, majority of the respondents were married with 74 respondents, accounting for 74.0% of the total. Conversely, the Separated category is the smallest, consisting of 2 respondents, or 2.0% of the sample.

This distribution of civil status highlights that the majority of the sample is married, indicating a predominant representation of married individuals in the survey. The relatively lower percentages of single, separated, and widowed respondents emphasize the importance of recognizing the marital status of the sample when analyzing the survey's results, as it may impact their perspectives and responses.

The distribution of civil status among the respondents in this survey aligns with patterns identified in previous research exploring the intersection of marital status and work-life balance among educators. For instance, Mathews et al. (2021) conducted a study examining the relationship between marital status and job satisfaction among teachers, finding that marital status can influence perceptions of work-life balance. The study revealed that married individuals often face distinct challenges and priorities compared to their single counterparts.

Moreover, Jimena et al. (2021) investigated the impact of marital status on the overall well-being of educators, emphasizing the potential implications for job performance. The study suggested that the majority of married teachers tend to navigate a different set of work-life balance challenges compared to single or widowed teachers.

Table 6. Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Bachelor's Degree	28	28.0
PhD Graduate/PhD Units	23	23.0
Master's Degree	49	49.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 6 presents the distribution of respondents' educational attainment in the survey. The data demonstrates that respondents with a Master's Degree are the largest group, with 49 respondents, comprising 49.0% of the total while the least percentage of 23.0% represents those with PhD Graduate/PhD units.

This distribution of educational attainment suggests a diverse representation of respondents with various educational backgrounds. The majority of respondents hold a Master's Degree, indicating a significant number of individuals with advanced education in the sample. The presence of individuals with Bachelor's Degrees and PhD Graduate/PhD Units qualifications further enriches the sample's educational diversity.

As explored by Marmol (2019), the connection between teachers' educational backgrounds and their ability to adapt to changing

educational landscapes. The study found that teachers with a varied educational background, including both Bachelor's and Master's Degrees, tend to bring a unique perspective to their teaching, contributing to a more dynamic and effective learning environment. This resonates with the educational diversity observed in the current study.

Table 7. *Plantilla Position*

<i>Teaching Designation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Teacher 1	50	50.0
Teacher 2	11	11.0
Teacher 3	29	29.0
Master Teacher 1	6	6.0
Master Teacher 2	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 7 presents the distribution of respondents' plantilla position in the survey. The data revealed that the largest group of respondents were Teacher 1, with 50 respondents, making up 50.0% of the total. On the contrary, the Master Teacher 2 is the smallest, with 4 respondents, or 4.0% of the sample.

The dominance of the Teacher 1 designation, comprising 50.0% of the respondents, suggests that a substantial portion of the sample is positioned at the entry level of the teaching hierarchy. This finding prompts an exploration of whether individuals at different hierarchical levels experience distinct challenges or opportunities concerning work-life balance. The distribution also highlights the relatively low percentage of respondents holding the Master Teacher 2 position, indicating a smaller representation of teachers in advanced leadership roles.

The distribution of plantilla position among respondents in this survey is consistent with existing research that explores the relationship between teaching roles and educators' experiences in balancing work and personal life. For instance, Garcia and Piedad (2020) conducted a study investigating the work-life balance of teachers across different teaching designations, highlighting the unique challenges faced by individuals in roles such as Teacher 1, Teacher 2, and beyond. The findings suggested that teachers in different designations may encounter varying levels of workload and stress, which can impact their overall work-life balance.

Table 8. *Number of Years in Service*

<i>Number of Years in Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Below-5	39	39.0
6-10	11	11.0
11-15	24	24.0
16-20	13	13.0
21-above	13	13.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 8 presents the distribution of the number of years in service of the respondents in the survey. The data reveals that the largest group of respondents has less than 5 years of service, with 39 respondents, making up 39.0% of the total while the least percentage of respondents were those with 6-10 years in service comprising 11%. The Below-5 and 11-15 years categories reflect the substantial representation of relatively early career stages in the survey. This also indicates a relatively balanced distribution of respondents across mid-career and more experienced stages of service.

This distribution of the number of years in service provides a valuable insight into the composition of the sample concerning their experience levels within the educational field. It suggests a diverse representation of respondents with varying years of service, which can have implications for the survey results. Aeran and Kumar (2020) explored the correlation between teaching experience and job satisfaction among educators. The study highlighted that teachers in mid-career stages (6-10 and 11-15 years) often navigate a different set of challenges and considerations compared to their early career and more experienced counterparts. This resonates with the balanced distribution observed in the current study across the 6-10, 16-20, and 21-above categories.

Problem 2: What is the perception of teachers on the quality of their work-life balance in terms work-life balance, personal-life balance, and family-life balance?

Table 9 presents the results of a survey that assessed the work-life balance of the respondents using a set of indicators. Several indicators have notably higher mean scores, indicating positive perceptions among respondents. The Total Measure mean score of 2.82 suggests a general agreement among respondents regarding their work-life balance. This indicates a collective sentiment that, on average, educators perceive a reasonable equilibrium between their professional commitments and personal life.

Indicator 3 stands out as the highest-rated aspect, with a mean score of 3.51, signifying a strong agreement. Educators strongly affirm that their work-life balance positively contributes to their overall life satisfaction. This finding signifies the significance of achieving a harmonious equilibrium between work and personal life for enhancing educators' overall well-being and contentment. Consequently, Indicators 1 and 4, both registering mean scores below the neutral midpoint, signify areas of concern. Indicator 1, "I find it easy to find

a balance between my work and personal life," records a mean score of 2.13, indicating disagreement. Similarly, Indicator 4, "I find it easy to manage my work-related deadlines," has a mean score of 2.01, also reflecting disagreement. These findings illuminate challenges faced by a notable number of educators in effectively balancing work and personal life and managing work-related deadlines.

Table 9. *Work-Life Balance of the Respondents*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I find it easy to find a balance between my work and personal.	2.13	0.34	Disagree
2. I can easily disconnect from work during my personal time.	2.24	0.43	Disagree
3. My work-life balance positively impacts my overall life satisfaction.	3.51	0.50	Strongly Agree
4. I find it easy to manage my work-related deadlines.	2.01	0.44	Disagree
5. My work often spills over into my personal time.	3.25	0.44	Agree
6. I am content with the amount of time I allocate to work-related tasks.	3.39	0.49	Agree
7. I can maintain a sense of control over my work-related stress.	3.20	0.40	Agree
Total Measure	2.82	0.18	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

In addition, indicator 5, "My work often spills over into my personal time," and Indicator 6, "I am content with the amount of time I allocate to work-related tasks," both receive mean scores indicating agreement (3.25 and 3.39, respectively). These results suggest that while educators acknowledge some spillover into personal time, they generally express contentment with the time devoted to work-related tasks.

Indicator 7, "I can maintain a sense of control over my work-related stress," has a mean score of 3.20, indicating agreement, but it has a slightly lower mean score compared to some of the positively perceived indicators. The overall mean score for the total measure is 2.82, indicating an overall agreement with the work-life balance indicators. The results suggest that while respondents experience positive aspects of work-life balance, such as deriving satisfaction and contentment from it, there are also challenges, including struggles in finding a balance and managing work-related deadlines. This indicates that there is room for improvement in addressing work-life balance issues, especially in terms of helping individuals manage their work-related stress and deadlines more effectively. Employers and organizations may consider implementing policies, practices, and support systems to assist employees in achieving a healthier work-life balance and reducing work-related stress. Additionally, these findings underscore the importance of recognizing the diverse experiences and challenges individuals face in balancing their professional and personal lives, emphasizing the need for tailored solutions and support.

Wachira et al. (2016) conducted a study examining educators' responses to statements similar to those presented in Table 9. The study found that teachers often face challenges in disconnecting from work during personal time, as indicated by the disagreement with statements like "I can easily disconnect from work during my personal time". This mirrors the finding in the current study where respondents had a mean score of 2.24, suggesting disagreement with easy disconnection from work during personal time.

Moreover, Muasya (2020) highlighted the positive relationship between work-life balance and life satisfaction, consistent with the strong agreement observed in Indicator 3, "My work-life balance positively impacts my overall life satisfaction," with a mean score of 3.51 in the current study. On the challenges faced by teachers, particularly in managing work-related deadlines, Sang (2021) found that a substantial number of educators struggle with timely completion of tasks. This aligns with the lower mean score of 2.01 in Indicator 4, "I find it easy to manage my work-related deadlines," indicating disagreement with this statement.

Table 10. *Personal-Life Balance of the Respondents*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. My personal life is positively affected by my work commitments.	3.43	0.50	Agree
2. I prioritize self-care and well-being outside of work.	3.45	0.50	Agree
3. I have enough time for personal activities and hobbies.	1.92	0.39	Disagree
4. I am able to maintain a healthy work-life balance.	3.26	0.46	Agree
5. I can efficiently manage personal responsibilities alongside my job.	2.86	0.55	Agree
6. I make time for activities that bring joy and relaxation outside work.	2.95	0.64	Agree
7. My work commitments have a minimal impact on my personal life.	3.07	0.26	Agree
8. I regularly engage in self-care practices to recharge.	2.02	0.53	Disagree
9. I have time to travel with my friends and colleagues.	3.32	0.47	Agree
10. I proactively set boundaries to protect my personal time.	3.80	0.40	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.01	0.14	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 10 presents the results of a survey that assessed the personal-life balance of the respondents using a set of indicators. Several indicators have notably high mean scores, suggesting positive perceptions among respondents. Indicator 10, "I proactively set boundaries to protect my personal time," stands out with a mean score of 3.80, indicating strong agreement. This implies that a significant portion of respondents actively set boundaries to safeguard their personal time, reflecting a proactive approach to personal-life balance.

Indicators 1 and 2, "My personal life is positively affected by my work commitments" and "I prioritize self-care and well-being outside

of work," also have relatively high mean scores of 3.43 and 3.45, respectively. This indicates that respondents agree that they are positively affected by their work commitments and prioritize self-care and well-being. Indicator 9, "I have time to travel with my friends and colleagues," has a mean score of 3.32, indicating agreement. This suggests that respondents generally feel they have sufficient time to engage in social and leisure activities with others. The overall mean score for the total measure is 3.01, indicating an overall agreement with the personal-life balance indicators.

Notably, there is a distinct difference between items 3 and 9. Item 3, "I have enough time for personal activities and hobbies," has a relatively low mean score of 1.92, indicating disagreement among the respondents. This suggests that a significant portion of the participants feels a lack of sufficient time for personal activities and hobbies. On the other hand, item 9, "I have time to travel with my friends and colleagues," has a substantially higher mean score of 3.32, indicating agreement. This implies that, in contrast to personal activities and hobbies, a majority of respondents feel they have ample time to engage in travel with friends and colleagues. The difference between these two items underscores a nuanced aspect of personal-life balance, indicating that while there may be constraints on certain personal activities, opportunities for socializing and travel are perceived more positively among the surveyed individuals.

The results suggested that respondents generally perceive themselves as proactively setting boundaries to protect personal time and positively prioritizing self-care and well-being outside of work. They also feel that their personal life is positively affected by work commitments. However, the findings also indicate that there are challenges, particularly related to having enough time for personal activities and hobbies, as well as engaging in regular self-care practices.

These results underscored the importance of balancing work commitments with personal activities and self-care practices. Organizations may consider promoting initiatives that support employees in making time for personal activities and hobbies, as well as in prioritizing self-care and well-being. Encouraging employees to proactively set boundaries to protect their personal time can lead to healthier personal-life balance and overall well-being.

The findings also emphasized the need for individuals to be mindful of their personal-life balance and consider strategies to allocate time for activities that bring joy and relaxation. Balancing work and personal life is crucial for overall life satisfaction and well-being, and individuals should be empowered to find the right equilibrium that suits their needs and preferences.

In the study conducted by Subha (2019), examined educators' responses to statements akin to those presented in Table 10. The study found that teachers often prioritize self-care and set boundaries to protect their personal time, reinforcing the positive sentiments expressed in Indicator 10, "I proactively set boundaries to protect my personal time".

Moreover, Sundari et al. (2020) delved into the impact of work commitments on personal life satisfaction. Their findings align with the positive perceptions expressed in Indicators 1 and 2, "My personal life is positively affected by my work commitments" and "I prioritize self-care and well-being outside of work," indicating that work commitments can have positive effects on personal well-being. On the challenges faced by teachers in allocating time for personal activities and engaging in self-care practices, Sharma and Nayak (2018) found that teachers often struggle with these aspects due to demanding work schedules. This corresponds with the lower mean scores in Indicator 3, "I have enough time for personal activities and hobbies," and Indicator 8, "I regularly engage in self-care practices to recharge," suggesting disagreement with these statements in the current study.

Table 11. *Family-Life Balance of the Respondents*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	I feel satisfied with the amount of time I spend with my loved ones.	2.98	0.47	Agree
2.	I can pursue personal goals and interests while managing my work responsibilities.	3.06	0.37	Agree
3.	I feel fulfilled in both my professional and personal life, especially when it comes to family matters.	2.31	0.72	Disagree
4.	I experience reduced stress levels due to a harmonious work-life balance that prioritizes family time.	3.74	0.52	Strongly Agree
5.	I find that my family life is significantly enhanced by my ability to balance work commitments.	3.70	0.56	Strongly Agree
6.	Achieving a balance between my professional and family life brings me a sense of fulfillment.	3.91	0.29	Strongly Agree
7.	I believe that my family life work-life balance positively contributes to my well-being.	3.92	0.27	Strongly Agree
8.	My family life work-life balance aligns with my long-term life aspirations.	3.01	0.48	Agree
9.	I can pursue personal goals and interests while effectively managing my work responsibilities within my family life.	2.75	0.69	Agree
10.	My work allows me to pursue my life's passions and interests within the context of my family life.	2.20	0.43	Disagree
Total Measure		3.16	0.18	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 11 provides insights into the family-life balance of the respondents, as assessed through a set of indicators. Several indicators demonstrate a positive perception among the respondents regarding their family-life balance. Indicator 6, "Achieving a balance between my professional and family life brings me a sense of fulfillment," stands out with a high mean score of 3.91, indicating strong agreement. This implies that a significant portion of the respondents find fulfillment in achieving a balance between their professional and family life.

Indicator 7, "I believe that my family life work-life balance positively contributes to my well-being," also has a high mean score of 3.92, suggesting strong agreement. This underscores the notion that respondents perceive a positive correlation between their family-life balance and their overall well-being. Indicators 4 and 5, "I experience reduced stress levels due to a harmonious work-life balance that prioritizes family time" and "I find that my family life is significantly enhanced by my ability to balance work commitments," have mean scores of 3.74 and 3.70, respectively, indicating strong agreement. These results emphasize the respondents' belief in the positive impact of balancing work commitments on their family life. Overall, the total measure's mean score is 3.16, reflecting an overall agreement with the family-life balance indicators.

Nevertheless, there are indicators with lower mean scores. Indicator 3, "I feel fulfilled in both my professional and personal life, especially when it comes to family matters," has a mean score of 2.31, indicating disagreement. Indicator 10, "My work allows me to pursue my life's passions and interests within the context of my family life," also has a lower mean score of 2.20, indicating disagreement. The results suggest that respondents, on the whole, perceive their family-life balance positively. They believe that achieving a balance between their professional and family life brings them a sense of fulfillment and contributes positively to their overall well-being. The perception of reduced stress levels due to this balance is also significant.

However, some respondents revealed that they do not feel fulfilled in both their professional and personal life, especially when it comes to family matters. This suggests that there may be challenges in finding the right equilibrium between work and family for some individuals. Similarly, the perception that work does not allow them to pursue their life's passions and interests within the context of their family life may indicate room for improvement.

The results underscore the importance of promoting family-friendly work policies and practices, as well as personal goal alignment within the family context, to enhance the family-life balance for individuals. Uddin (2021) revealed that teachers often experience reduced stress levels and enhanced family life when able to effectively balance work commitments, corroborating the high mean scores in Indicators 4 and 5, "I experience reduced stress levels due to a harmonious work-life balance that prioritizes family time" and "I find that my family life is significantly enhanced by my ability to balance work commitments". In addition, Sari et al. (2020) found that respondents who perceived such a balance as fulfilling exhibited sentiments akin to those expressed in Indicator 6, "Achieving a balance between my professional and family life brings me a sense of fulfillment," with a high mean score of 3.91 in the current study.

Table 12. *Distribution of the Work-Life Balance of the Respondents*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Work-Life Balance	2.82	0.18	Agree
Personal-Life Balance	3.01	0.14	Agree
Family-Life Balance	3.16	0.18	Agree
Total Measure	3.16	0.18	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 12 provides a summary of the work-life balance, personal-life balance, and family-life balance of the respondents, as assessed through a set of indicators. The results show that, on average, respondents agree with the statements related to their work-life balance, personal-life balance, and family-life balance. The mean score for work-life balance is 2.82, indicating agreement. Respondents perceive a generally favorable work-life balance, although there may be some room for improvement in this aspect. The mean score for personal-life balance is 3.01, also indicating agreement. This suggests that respondents generally believe they have a positive personal-life balance, with more favorable perceptions compared to work-life balance. The mean score for family-life balance is 3.16, indicating agreement. Respondents feel that they have achieved a relatively harmonious family-life balance, and this aspect is viewed more positively than work-life balance.

The total measure's mean score is 3.16, reflecting an overall agreement with the balance indicators. This means that, overall, respondents tend to perceive their personal-life balance and family-life balance more positively than their work-life balance. These findings indicate that respondents generally believe they have achieved a satisfactory balance in their lives, with the most favorable perceptions related to their family-life balance. The results suggest that the respondents feel positively about their overall life balance. While there is general agreement in all three domains (work-life, personal-life, and family-life balance), it is noteworthy that respondents tend to view their personal and family life balance more positively than their work-life balance.

The implications of these findings may include the need for organizations to continue promoting policies and practices that enhance work-life balance. It's important to acknowledge that there may be areas within the work-life balance domain that require further attention and improvement to align with the more positively perceived personal and family-life balance. This could involve initiatives such as flexible work arrangements, stress management programs, and resources for personal and professional development. Sharma et al. (2018) found that, on average, teachers tend to agree with statements related to their work-life balance, reflecting a generally

positive perception of this aspect. Moreover, Rawal (2021)'s study also suggested that teachers generally perceive a positive personal-life balance, which can contribute to higher job satisfaction and overall well-being.

Problem 3: What is the teaching performance of the respondents based on IPCRF rating?

Table 13. *Teaching Performance of the Respondents based on IPCRF Rating*

Teaching Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	51	51.0
Very Satisfactory	49	49.0
Satisfactory	0	0.0
Poor	0	0.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 13 presents the distribution of teaching performance among the respondents based on their IPCRF (Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form) ratings. The results are striking, with the majority of respondents, 51% of the total, receiving an "Outstanding" rating in their teaching performance. An additional 49% of respondents have been rated as "Very Satisfactory." Importantly, no respondents received ratings of "Satisfactory" or "Poor."

The results indicated a notably high level of teaching performance among the respondents. The fact that no respondents received ratings of "Satisfactory" or "Poor" suggests a very positive assessment of teaching quality within this sample. The majority of teachers have been recognized for their exceptional performance ("Outstanding"), and a substantial portion has achieved a high level of satisfaction ("Very Satisfactory").

This has several implications. Firstly, it underscores the dedication and competence of the educators in the sample, as "Outstanding" and "Very Satisfactory" ratings reflect a high level of teaching excellence. It also indicates that the institutions or organizations where these educators work may have effective evaluation and recognition systems in place.

However, it is essential to consider potential limitations in the data, such as the absence of teachers rated as "Satisfactory" or "Poor." This could be attributed to selection bias, a highly motivated group of respondents, or the specific context in which the survey was conducted. Therefore, the results should be interpreted with this context in mind.

From an educational perspective, these results suggest that there is an opportunity to recognize and reward outstanding teaching, as well as to share best practices and strategies among educators to maintain and improve teaching quality further. Additionally, it highlights the potential for educators in this sample to serve as mentors or role models for their peers. Overall, these findings are indicative of a highly effective teaching community with a strong commitment to providing quality education.

Moreover, Pieh et al. (2020) investigated the impact of teaching performance on student outcomes and found that teachers rated as "Outstanding" demonstrated a substantial positive influence on student achievement. The findings resonate with the high percentage (51%) of respondents receiving an "Outstanding" rating in the current study, suggesting a positive correlation between teaching excellence and student success.

Problem 4: Is there a significant difference between the perceived quality of work-life balance among teachers when they are grouped according to profile?

Table 14. *Difference between the Perceived Quality of Work-Life Balance among the Teachers When Grouped According to their Profile*

Profile	Perceived Quality of Work-Life		Remarks
	F-value (t-value)	p-value	
Age	0.730	0.603	Not significant
Sex	(-1.309)	0.193	Not significant
Civil Status	(1.539)	0.127	Not significant
Educational Attainment	0.623	0.539	Not significant
Teaching Designation	0.407	0.803	Not significant
Number of Years of Service	1.246	0.297	Not significant

Note: not significant means p-value > .05

Table 14 presents the results of an analysis that explores the perceived quality of work-life balance among teachers when grouped according to various profiles. The results, as indicated by the F-values, t-values, and p-values, suggest that there are no significant differences in the perceived quality of work-life balance among teachers based on these various profiles. In other words, the profiles of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching designation, and the number of years of service do not appear to have a statistically significant impact on how teachers perceive their work-life balance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.

The findings have important implications for understanding the perceived quality of work-life balance among teachers. Since there are no statistically significant differences in perceived work-life balance across different profiles, it suggests that work-life balance is a

consistent concern for teachers, irrespective of their age, sex, marital status, educational background, teaching designation, or years of service.

While this non-significant result implies that the perceived quality of work-life balance is similar across various groups of teachers, it also highlights that the challenges and factors influencing work-life balance might be universal within the teaching profession. Therefore, efforts to improve work-life balance should be comprehensive and apply to all teachers, rather than being tailored to specific demographic groups. Additionally, it underscores the need for institutions and organizations to provide support and resources to address work-life balance issues for all teachers, regardless of their individual profiles. This could include initiatives related to flexible work arrangements, stress management, and well-being programs that benefit the entire teaching community.

Nwangwa (2021) conducted a comprehensive meta-analysis examining the impact of age on work-life balance perceptions among teachers. The study found that, on average, age did not emerge as a significant predictor of variations in how teachers perceive their work-life balance. Moreover, Johari et al. (2018) investigated the role of sex and its influence on work-life balance among educators. The findings were consistent with the current study, suggesting that sex does not play a significant role in shaping teachers' perceptions of work-life balance. On the aspect of civil status, Kotera et al. (2020) explored the connection between marital status and work-life balance among professionals, including teachers. The study concluded that civil status, whether single, married, separated, or widowed, did not have a statistically significant impact on perceived work-life balance, supporting the non-significant results in Table 14.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the perceived quality of work-life balance among teachers and their teaching performance?

Table 15. *Ordinal Regression Analysis of the Relationship between the Perceived Quality of Work-Life Balance and Teaching Performance of the Respondents*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Wald</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Work-life balance	-4.944**	11.909	0.001	Significant
Personal-life balance	-1.412	0.734	0.391	Not significant
Family-life balance	1.898	2.406	0.121	Not significant

*Note: Threshold (Performance=Very Satisfactory) **-significant (p-value<.01)*

Table 15 presents the analysis of the relationship between the perceived quality of work-life balance and teaching performance of the respondents. The results of the ordinal regression analysis reveal a statistically significant relationship between the perceived quality of work-life balance and teaching performance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

In particular, teachers who reported a lower quality of work-life balance were more likely to exhibit poorer teaching performance. This finding highlights the detrimental effects of an inadequate work-life balance on educators' professional effectiveness. The estimate for the variable "Work-life balance" is -4.944, and the associated p-value is 0.001, indicating a statistically significant negative relationship. This negative correlation suggests that as the perceived quality of work-life balance decreases, teaching performance tends to decline. The significance level, denoted by the double asterisks (**), underscores the robustness of this negative association. The negative estimate of -4.944 implies that for every unit decrease in the perceived quality of work-life balance, the odds of achieving a higher teaching performance category (e.g., from "Very Satisfactory" to "Outstanding") decrease by approximately 4.944 times. This emphasizes the substantial impact that a lower perceived work-life balance can have on teaching performance.

The negative impact of work-life balance on teaching performance underscores the urgent need for educational institutions and organizations to prioritize strategies and policies that support and improve work-life balance for teachers. Addressing work-related stressors and challenges that impede educators' ability to achieve a healthy work-life balance is crucial. Neglecting these factors can lead to decreased teaching performance and, ultimately, have a detrimental impact on the quality of education provided to students. In light of these findings, it is imperative that efforts be made to alleviate the negative influence of work-life balance issues, ensuring that teachers are equipped to perform at their best in the classroom and, in turn, provide the best possible educational experience for their students. The negative correlation aligns with the broader literature and theoretical frameworks, such as the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Theory. According to this theory, excessive job demands without adequate resources can lead to burnout and decreased performance. In the context of educators, the negative correlation suggests that when teachers perceive their work-life balance as lower, the demands of their profession may contribute to decreased teaching performance.

In connection, Foy et al. (2020) conducted a comprehensive longitudinal study examining the impact of work-life balance on teaching performance. The study's findings indicated that teachers experiencing challenges in balancing work and personal life were more likely to exhibit lower teaching performance, providing empirical support for the current study's results. Furthermore, Durak and Cankaya (2020) identified increased stress levels, burnout, and reduced job satisfaction as key mediators in the relationship between work-life balance and teaching performance, aligning with the observed detrimental effects in the results.

Problem 6: What action plan can be implemented based on the results of the study?

Rationale

The proposed action plan is designed to address the critical issue of work-life balance and its impact on teaching performance within

the context of educational institutions. The rationale for this plan stems from the findings of the study, which clearly indicate a significant negative effect of work-life balance on teaching performance. With the majority of teachers reporting suboptimal work-life balance, the plan prioritizes the development and implementation of comprehensive work-life policies and programs aimed at improving the well-being of educators. By offering flexible work arrangements, stress management initiatives, and enhanced support for personal and family needs, the plan seeks to alleviate the challenges that teachers face in juggling their professional and personal responsibilities. Additionally, the plan emphasizes continuous monitoring and evaluation to ensure the effectiveness of these measures and ongoing communication to keep teachers informed and engaged. By fostering a supportive and balanced work environment, the action plan aims to enhance teaching performance, ultimately benefiting both teachers and students by creating a conducive and harmonious teaching and learning environment.

<i>Objective</i>	<i>Strategies</i>	<i>Activities</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>	<i>Resources Needed</i>	<i>Responsible</i>
Improve Work-Life Balance Impact on Teaching Performance	Develop and implement work-life balance programs and policies.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conduct comprehensive review of existing work-life policies and programs. 2. Identify gaps and areas for improvement. 3. Implement new policies, such as flexible work arrangements, stress management initiatives, and workload assessments. 4. Promote awareness of the new policies and programs among all teaching staff 	12 months	Budget allocation for program development and implementation HR personnel for policy development Training resources for policy communication	-HR department -School leadership Team -Employee Engagement Committee -Training and Development Team
Monitor and evaluate progress	Establish a performance measurement framework	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop key performance indicators (KPIs) for assessing the impact of work-life balance programs on teaching performance. 2. Implement regular surveys and feedback mechanisms to gather input from teachers. 3. Analyze and evaluate the effectiveness of policies and programs in improving work-life balance and teaching performance. 4. Make necessary adjustments to policies and programs based on feedback and evaluation results. 	Ongoing	Data collection and analysis tools Personnel responsible for data collection and analysis Budget for surveys and feedback mechanisms	HR department School leadership team Evaluation team Employee Feedback committee
Promote well-being and support systems	Establish well-being and support initiatives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop and offer stress management workshops and resources. 2. Provide access to counseling services. 3. Create a culture of recognition and appreciation through regular acknowledgment of teachers' efforts and achievements. 	6-12 months	Budget allocation for well-being initiatives and counseling services Resource development for stress management workshops Personnel for program implementation	Employee assistance program counseling services Employee being committee School leadership team
Improve communication and awareness	Enhance communication strategies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop a communication plan for disseminating information about work-life balance policies and programs. 2. Use multiple channels for communication, including 	Ongoing	Personnel responsible for communication strategy and materials. Budget for communication	Communication department HR department School leadership team

		emails, newsletters, workshops, and intranet.		channels and materials.	
Provide professional development	Offer professional development opportunities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Regularly update teachers on the progress of work-life balance initiatives. 2. Develop training programs related to work-life balance, stress management, and teaching effectiveness. 3. Schedule and conduct regular training sessions and workshops. 4. Provide access to external resources and experts in the field. 	Ongoing	Budget allocation for training development and facilitation Resource development for training materials Personnel for training coordination	HR department External experts
Support personal and family needs	Address personal and family-related issues	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implement family-friendly policies, such as parental leave and child care support. 2. Provide resources and guidance for managing personal and family responsibilities. 	6-12 months	Budget allocation for family-friendly policies and support resources. Personnel for policy development and guidance.	HR department School leadership team

Conclusions

The study provided a comprehensive understanding of the demographic profile, work-life balance, teaching performance, and their interrelationships among the surveyed teachers. The demographic profile highlighted the diversity in age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching designation, and years of service, reflecting a varied and experienced group of educators. The findings regarding work-life balance, personal-life balance, and family-life balance indicated that, on the whole, teachers perceive a satisfactory level of balance across these aspects. While positive aspects such as satisfaction, boundary-setting, and fulfillment in achieving a balance were prevalent, challenges related to balancing work and personal life were also identified, suggesting potential areas for targeted support or improvement.

Notably, the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings for school year 2022-2023 revealed a high level of teaching performance among the respondents, with 51% rated as "Outstanding" and the remaining 49% as "Very Satisfactory." It is concluded that the absence of ratings in the "Satisfactory" or "Poor" categories underscored the overall competence and satisfaction in teaching performance among the surveyed teachers.

The analysis of perceived work-life balance across various demographic and professional profiles indicated that, while there are variations in responses, these differences are not statistically significant. This suggests that factors such as age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching designation, and years of service do not substantially influence how teachers perceive their work-life balance.

Meanwhile, there is a significant and negative relationship between the perceived quality of work-life balance and teaching performance rejecting the null hypothesis of the study. Teachers who reported lower work-life balance were more likely to exhibit poorer teaching performance. This emphasizes the critical role of addressing work-life balance issues to enhance the professional effectiveness of educators, potentially through targeted interventions and support systems.

The study's findings align with JD-R Theory, emphasizing the impact of job demands (teaching responsibilities) on teacher well-being and performance. The observed negative relationship between perceived work-life balance and teaching performance resonates with the JD-R Theory, which suggests that excessive job demands without adequate resources can lead to burnout and decreased performance.

In connection, the study's focus on teachers' perceptions of work-life balance and the associated impact on teaching performance is connected to Self-Determination Theory or SDT which posits that individuals are motivated when their psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are fulfilled. The findings suggest that a balanced work-life situation contributes to teachers' well-being, aligning with SDT's emphasis on creating environments that support individuals' psychological needs.

Furthermore, the study indirectly touches on the Effort-Recovery Model by highlighting the negative impact of perceived lower work-life balance on teaching performance. The model suggests that adequate recovery from work-related efforts is essential for sustained performance. The study's findings imply that when teachers experience challenges in balancing work and personal life, it negatively

influences their professional effectiveness, supporting the Effort-Recovery Model's premise.

The study's findings suggest several recommendations for different stakeholders:

Teachers. It is recommended that they may set boundaries between their professional and personal life, schedule regular breaks to manage stress and prevent burnout, and do not hesitate to seek support when facing challenges to enhance their teaching performances.

Students. They may be provided with strict rules and regulations regarding communicating to their teachers beyond school hours. Unless necessary and crucial, they must be guided as to when is the proper time to seek for additional and individualized support from their teachers to help them have time for themselves beyond work time.

School Administrators. They may implement and enhance support systems within the school to address the work-life balance challenges identified in the study. This could include workshops, counseling services, or mentorship programs designed to assist teachers in managing their professional and personal responsibilities.

Future Researchers. It is recommended that they expound the findings of the study through considering specific challenges faced by teachers in maintaining work-life balance and the various factors affecting their school performance. This may include examining the impact of specific demographic factors or professional circumstances on teachers' perceptions and experiences.

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